

Biomechanical factors involved in coating transfer during drug-coated balloon angioplasty: A computational analysis

Efstathios Stratakos¹, Gianluca Poletti¹, Luca Antonini¹, Lorenza Petrini² and Giancarlo Pennati¹

1. LaBS, Dept. of Chemistry, Materials and Chemical Engineering “Giulio Natta”, Politecnico di Milano, Milan, Italy

2. Dept. of Civil and Environmental Engineering, Politecnico di Milano, Milan, Italy

Aims: The present study focused on biomechanical factors, so far understudied into the literature, that may affect the coating transfer to the arterial wall and the performances of drug-coated balloons (DCBs).

Introduction: DCBs have emerged as a potential treatment option for arterial lesions due to their theoretical ability to uniformly deliver drug-coating to the arterial wall, providing proper antiproliferative drug sources also after the balloon deflation to avoid arterial restenosis. However, some clinical studies have shown no superior efficacy compared to drug-eluting stents, possibly due to restrained coating delivery (1). This was recently confirmed by animal studies that revealed sparse coating distribution onto the arterial wall, suggesting insufficient contact pressures in some areas (2). To address this issue, a numerical investigation of the mechanical interaction between DCB and arteries during balloon inflation is here proposed to assess the role played by various biomechanical parameters with respect to the transfer of the coating onto the arterial wall.

Methods: Detailed models of DCBs are developed, taking into account the balloon folding and the variability of wall thickness due to molding manufacturing process. Moreover, various arterial models are considered to mimic both healthy arteries, as in the animal studies, and human diseased arteries as in clinical treatments. The effect of a number of parameters of the balloon (e.g. number of folds, compliance), the artery (e.g. lumen diameter, compliance, plaque stiffness) and their interaction (oversizing, friction) are extensively studied by means of finite element simulations. Two important quantities are calculated during the balloon inflation: local contact pressures, associated with adhesion of the coating to the arterial wall, and local balloon stretches, possibly causing the detachment of the coating from the balloon.

Results and discussion: The obtained color maps reveal clear spatial heterogeneous distributions for both the contact pressure and the balloon stretch for all the investigated conditions. In particular, the balloon unfolding causes an irregular balloon-artery interaction, creating a linearly patterned distribution that is more evident with high friction coefficients. Moreover, the thicker wall at the two balloon ends causes a notable reduction of local contact pressures. Both these results are consistent with the peculiar coating transfer observed in some animal studies (2), confirming the role of contact

pressures. Finally, for a fixed value of inflation pressure, the average contact pressure significantly depends on all the other investigated parameters. Nevertheless, considering that the drug-coating characteristics are highly variable across the commercial DCBs, an additional in vitro analysis (3) has to be combined with the in silico outcomes to reveal the effect of these heterogeneous contact pressures and balloon stretches on the coating transfer for a specific device.

Acknowledgments: This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under the Marie Skłodowska-Curie grant agreement n° 956470.

References

2. Cao Z, Li J, Fang Z, Feierkaiti Y, Zheng X, Jiang X. The factors influencing the efficiency of drug-coated balloons. *Front Cardiovasc Med*. 2022 12;9:947776.
3. Tzafriri AR, Muraj B, Garcia-Polite F, Salazar-Martín AG, Markham P, Zani B, et al. Balloon-based drug coating delivery to the artery wall is dictated by coating micro-morphology and angioplasty pressure gradients. *Biomaterials*. 2020;260:120337.
4. Chang GH, Azar DA, Lyle C, Chitalia VC, Shazly T, Kolachalama VB. Intrinsic coating morphology modulates acute drug transfer in drug-coated balloon therapy. *Sci Rep*. 2019 2;9(1):6839.